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The organizational and economic aspects of management, efficiency of use and development of personnel at the enterprise under martial law

The subject of the research is the determination of the organizational and economic aspects of management, the efficiency of the use and development of personnel at an enterprise under martial law.

The aim of the research is to determine the main trends and the program of organizational and economic measures to improve the efficiency of the use of personnel at the enterprise under martial law.

Research methods. In the process of writing the article, general scientific and special methods were used to study economic phenomena and processes that are inherent in the study of enterprise personnel management under martial law.

Results of the investigation. Because of writing the article, it was found that with the start of a full-scale war between Russia and Ukraine, all processes in the state slowed down or almost stopped. It has been proven that this problem has not bypassed both employees and employers, where the latter have suffered losses due to the forced migration of their personnel in order to ensure their safety. It has been established that personnel management in the conditions of a full-scale war is manifested in a targeted impact on the organizational behavior of employees, aimed at activating their unused professional and spiritual capabilities, stabilizing the emotional state of subordinates and ensuring security for all enterprise personnel. It has been determined that one of the most important problems at present in the field of personnel management is to ensure the efficiency and further development of personnel in the enterprise, since it is the personnel, as a key factor, that will stand in the way of the country's recovery after a large-scale war.

Scope of the results. Labor economics, management, labor resources management, personnel potential, enterprise economics.

Conclusions. It has been determined that the formation, retention and development of the personnel of the enterprise, its effective use, ensuring the high quality of human resources in the future will become decisive factors in the efficiency of production and the competitiveness of products both for the enterprise in particular and for the country's economy as a whole. It has been proved that in order to determine the organizational and economic aspects of management, the effectiveness of the use and development of personnel at an enterprise under martial law, it is necessary to use the general trends in personnel management, based on the factors of influence that will take place in the post-war recovery of the country's economy.

Keywords: organizational and economic aspects, personnel management, personnel development, personnel utilization efficiency, enterprise, martial law.

ПУЗИРЬОВА П. В.

Організаційно-економічні аспекти управління, ефективності використання та розвитку персоналу на підприємстві в умовах воєнного стану

Предметом дослідження є визначення організаційно-економічних аспектів управління, ефективності використання та розвитку персоналу на підприємстві в умовах воєнного стану.

Метою дослідження є: визначення основних тенденцій та програми організаційно-економічних заходів щодо підвищення ефективності використання персоналу на підприємстві в умовах воєнного стану.

Методи дослідження. В процесі написання статті було використано загально-наукові та спеціальні методи дослідження економічних явищ та процесів, які притаманні дослідженню управління персоналу підприємства в умовах воєнного стану.

Результати роботи. В результаті написання статті було встановлено, що з початком повномасштабної війни Росії проти України уповільнились або майже зупинились всі процеси в державі. Доведено, що ця проблема не обійшла і найманих робітників і роботодавців, де останні понесли втрати через вимушену міграцію свого персоналу з метою забезпечення їх власної безпеки. Встановлено, що управління персоналом в умовах повномасштабної війни проявляється у цілеспрямованому впливі на організаційну поведінку працівників, що спрямована на активізацію їх невикористаних професійних і духовних можливостей, стабілізацію емоційного стану підлеглих, та забезпеченні безпеки для всього персоналу підприємства. Визначено, що однією з найважливіших проблем на даний час у галузі управління персоналом є забезпечення ефективності та подальшого розвитку персоналу на підприємстві, оскільки саме персонал, як ключовий фактор, постане на шляху відновлення країни у після масштабній війні.

Галузь застосування результатів. Економіка праці, менеджмент, управління трудовими ресурсами, кадровий потенціал, економіка підприємства.

Висновки. Визначено, що формування, збереження та розвиток персоналу підприємства, ефективне його використання, забезпечення високої якості кадрового потенціалу в найближчій перспективі стануть вирішальними факторами ефективності виробництва та конкурентоспроможності продукції як для підприємства в цілому, так і для економіки країни загалом. Доведено, що для визначення організаційно-економічних аспектів управління, ефективності використання та розвитку персоналу на підприємстві в умовах воєнного стану необхідно використовувати загальні тенденції щодо управління персоналом спираючись на чинники впливу, що матимуть місце у післявоєнному відновленні та відбудові економіки країни.

Ключові слова: організаційно-економічні аспекти, управління персоналом, розвиток персоналу, ефективність використання персоналу, підприємство, воєнний стан.

Formulation of the problem. With the beginning of the full-scale war of Russia against Ukraine, all processes in the state slowed down or almost stopped. This problem has not bypassed hired workers and employers, where the latter bear losses due to the forced migration of their personnel in order to ensure their own safety. Personnel management in the conditions of a full-scale war is manifested in a purposeful influence on the organizational behavior of employees, aimed at activating their unused professional and spiritual capabilities, stabilizing the emotional state of subordinates, and ensuring safety for all enterprise personnel. One of the most important problems at the moment in the field of personnel management is to ensure the efficiency and further development of the personnel at the enterprise, since it is the personnel, as a key factor, that will appear on the way to rebuilding the country after a large-scale war.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. Many works of various economists

are devoted to issues of personnel policy, personnel management, increasing the efficiency of its use, evaluation and motivation, among which are: I. Hnatenko, Yu. Kulikova, I. Dashko, Yu. Kakhovych, M. Shevchenko, T. Babenko, L. Lipych, O. Hrynkevych, O. Polinkevych, O. Lozhachevska, V. Safonova, T. Navrotska, I. Olmezova, V. Derhachova, O. Olshanskyi, M. Shkrobot, H. Didur, O. Shevchenko, I. Sedikova, K. Kozak, D. Sedikov, H. Chaban, V. Chyzh, Ya. Havrylenko, A. Chkheailo, I. Tkachenko, O. Sherstiuk, N. Zhuk, O. Voloshyna and others.

Presenting main material. In the conditions of martial law, the personnel policy of any enterprise is based on the close interaction of general principles of personnel management with specific tasks of market management [1; 2; 3]. The socio-psychological interaction of personnel, the training of management personnel and the social policy of the enterprise, the development of social partnership as a mechanism for the interconnection of this pol-

icity and the market economy are playing an increasingly important role today [4; 5; 6]. Due to military aggression from Russia, the process of adapting personnel at enterprises has become quite complicated, but remains relevant, as it is necessary to integrate new employees into teams and work processes. Thus, personnel management is part of the functional sphere of personnel policy as the main mechanism of the organization [7; 8].

With all the variety of existing approaches to this problem in different countries, the main and most general trends are the following (Fig. 1):

These general trends must be taken into account in the post-war reconstruction and production management during the reconstruction of the country's economy. Also, in the conditions of war, one of the most urgent problems is the issue of effective use of available labor resources, which is manifested in the creation at the enterprise of a scientifically based mechanism for managing personnel of various categories in the process of production and consumption of material goods while ensuring the optimization of the costs of the resources still available in the enterprise [12; 13; 14].

Measures to increase the efficiency of personnel use should include the following stages:

1. Determination and analysis of indicators of the formation and use of the company's personnel.
2. Search and analysis of reserves for increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel based on the information obtained during the analysis.
3. Development of a plan for the use of reserves to increase the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel, which should include specific terms

and measures for their implementation, provide for the financing of costs for these measures and the expected economic effect of their implementation, determine the responsible executors.

4. Development of employee motivation systems for achieving planned results.

5. Control over the implementation of measures provided for in the plan and the entire program, and regulation of their implementation.

6. Measurement and assessment of the real impact of the planned measures on increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of the company's personnel.

Now let us consider what is specifically included in each of the above stages.

1. Measurement and assessment of the company's existing personnel is the initial stage of the program. Its correct and successful implementation is an important prerequisite for the success of the following stages of the entire program. The most important thing at this stage is to ensure the reliability and comparability of indicators. In order to assess the existing level of personnel, it is necessary to know, in addition to the numerical characteristics of personnel, the volume of products produced and the costs of their production. It is quite difficult to compare these indicators, because in reality the enterprise produces a significant number of various products, which are difficult to compare and add. Universal value indicators of the number of products are not exempt from the influence of inflationary processes and spontaneous fluctuations in the market situation. It should also be constantly borne in mind that the resources used in production are interchangeable. That

Figure. 1. The main trends taking place in personnel management [9; 10; 11]

is, it is possible to reduce the amount of labor to achieve a certain useful effect by increasing the number of used means of production [15; 16].

2. The search and analysis of reserves for increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel is based on a comparison of the information obtained during the measurement and evaluation of the available personnel with the size necessary to obtain the maximum beneficial effect in this production. These reserves should also be sought in the processes of organization and personnel management.

3. When developing a plan for the use of reserves to increase the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel, it is necessary to ensure the coordination of the goals and objectives of the program. The plan should include specific measures aimed at the realization of the set goals, provide for the financing of costs for these measures.

4. The development of employee motivation systems for achieving the planned results is a necessary condition for the implementation of the program. Employees must know in advance how the planned results will affect the realization of their personal professional interests.

5. Control over the implementation of measures provided for by the plan and the entire program is necessary to identify and solve possible problems of their implementation at the initial stages, even before they become too serious. The starting point of the control process is the establishment of specific, time-bound goals that can be measured. In the control process, the actual and specified indicators or their components are compared, the scale of permissible deviations is determined.

6. Measurement and evaluation of the real impact of the planned measures on increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of the company's personnel potential is necessary in order to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of their implementation and to decide on priorities for the next period.

Among the main indicators of the social development of the company's employees in modern conditions should be increasing the qualifications of employees; improvement of working conditions and strengthening of health of employees; improvement of socio-cultural, housing, and communal conditions; social protection of members of the labor team [17; 18].

Figure 2. A program of organizational and economic measures to increase the efficiency of the use of personnel at the enterprise in the conditions of martial law [11; 14; 19; 20]

To form a program of organizational and economic measures of management, efficiency of use and development of personnel at the enterprise in the conditions of martial law, we will apply key factors that contribute to the optimization of costs for the enterprise's personnel. Thus, the intra-production reserves for increasing the efficiency of the use of personnel will be a reduction in the labor intensity of products, an improvement in the use of working time, an improvement in the organizational structure of enterprise management, and an improvement in the personnel training system and the improvement of their qualifications, taking into account progressive methods of production and labor, with the development of the enterprise's material, technological, and information base. The conducted analysis of the formation and use of the company's personnel, the factors of improvement of these indicators provided an opportunity to form the main directions of its development. In accordance with these directions, the company is developing a program to increase the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel. Therefore, it is possible to propose a program of organizational and economic measures to increase the efficiency of the use of personnel (Fig. 2) [19; 20].

Therefore, the proposed program of organizational and economic measures to increase the efficiency of personnel use involves: determination and analysis of indicators of the formation and use of personnel of the enterprise; search and analysis of reserves for increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel based on the information obtained during the analysis; development of a plan for the use of reserves for increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of personnel, which should include specific terms and measures for their implementation, provide for the financing of costs for these measures and the expected economic effect of their implementation, determine the responsible executors; development of employee motivation systems for achieving planned results; control over the implementation of measures provided for in the plan and the entire program, and regulation of their implementation; measurement and assessment of the real impact of the planned measures on increasing the efficiency of the formation and use of the company's personnel [2; 6; 10; 14].

Conclusions

The results of the activities of many enterprises during the period of military aggression show that the formation, preservation and development of enterprise personnel, their effective use, ensuring high-quality personnel potential will be decisive factors in the efficiency of production and competitiveness of products both for the enterprise as a whole and for the country's economy in general. Current issues regarding the use and development of personnel in the near future will be constantly in the center of attention of the management. Thus, to determine the organizational and economic aspects of management, the effectiveness of the use and development of personnel at the enterprise under martial law, it is necessary to use general trends in personnel management based on the factors of influence that will take place in the post-war recovery and reconstruction of the country's economy.

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Modeling the impact of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy

Relevance of the research topic. *An important requirement of the modern innovative economy is the need to satisfy the unlimited needs of society in conditions of limited production potential and human resources. Increasingly, the methodology and tools for solving this problem are based on the use of a system of aggregated production functions – classical economic–mathematical or statistical modeling, which allows analyzing quantitative changes, correlations and ratios between various factors of production (human resources, own or borrowed capital, labor, land, innovative activity, scientific and technical progress) and the volume of products that can be produced by the subject of entrepreneurial activity under the condition of effective combination of entrepreneurial potential. However, taking into account modern trends, there is a need for uninterrupted research of the production system of the enterprise in order to adjust the management.*

Formulation of the problem. *Currently, there are a large number of production functions: Alain, Cobb–Douglas, Solow, Cobb–Douglas–Gray, Leontiev, Menkiu–Romer, Georgescu–Roeden, CES–function, LES–function. For our research, the Cobb–Douglas production function is of particular interest, which, by its logical construction, allows us to take into account asymmetric trends in variable production, the uneven distribution of business resources, and in this way ensure greater validity of forecasts. Therefore, the study of the specifics of the Cobb–Douglas production function, as well as the foundations of its construction, is an important problem today that needs analysis.*

Setting the goal and tasks of the research – *to determine the main directions of modeling the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy.*

Research method or methodology. *The article uses the following methods: synthesis; modeling; abstraction; systematization and monographic generalization.*

Presentation of the main material. *Directions for modeling the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy are proposed. Forecasting of the impact of factors on the dynamics of the volume of sales of economic entities over the last eleven years was determined based on the use of the Cobb–Douglas production function.*

Field of application of results. *The proposed modeling can be used by business entities for the purpose of diagnosing production activities and making timely management decisions.*

Conclusions according to the article. *Modeling of the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy is proposed.*

Key words: *production function, forecasting, modeling, product realization, non–current assets, personnel, costs, entrepreneurship, economy, innovation, competitiveness*